

SELF-DIRECTED LEARNING: EMPOWERING MINDS FOR LIFELONG SUCCESS

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Abstract. The article deals with the priority direction of the study of foreign languages is determined in the current year in our republic, the necessity of Independent Education and lifelong learning during the whole life, as well as the opinions of scientists on the subject. In particular, the guidance and recommendations have been given for organizing and improving effectively of students' independent work at all stages of continuing education.

Keywords: *Self-directed learning (SDL)*, independent work, continuing education, innovative teaching technologies, independent language learning, self-assess, communicative exercises.

Nowadays, the students who are intelligent, creative, aspiring, and independent thinking are being created comfortable conditions and opportunities for studying effectively in our country. Shavkat Mirziyoyev the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, states that Mir Alisher Navoi, the great poet and founder of Uzbek literature, appealed to young people in his time and said: “If you want to shine, make a profession.” Indeed, a person who intends to shine a gracious light on people like the sun and willing to give a hand must master various sciences and professions. He also asserts that such achievements as our great ancestor said cannot be gained today without a thorough study of foreign languages. In the current year, Shavkat Mirziyoyev has proposed to make the study of foreign languages as a priority [1]. One of the main tasks of the university is to train specialists, effectively organize lessons and strengthen the responsibility of teachers in education process.

The needs and requirements for the socio-cultural, professional activities of future foreign language teachers require the introduction of innovative teaching technologies, active methods and new forms and ways of teaching. At the same time, independent work, group work projects, research and problem-solving elements are required to be included in the activities of students [3; 21]. Why is independent learning, that is, self-directed learning, important? The structure of our lives and activities requires the necessary ability to be always ready for all situations of life and activity, to constantly acquire new information and to make decisions with a sense of responsibility. There is a lot of talk about the need for lifelong learning throughout one's life. Self-directed learning refers to the outcome of creating an experience that empowers learners to make decisions about the information they want to become proficient in [6]. Brockett R.G., Hiemstra R. defined a learner self-direction as an individual's internal learning and growth process as well as the external influences experienced through instruction [4].

Self-directed learning includes six steps:

1. developing goals for study;

2. outlining assessment with respect to how the learner will know when they achieve those goals;
3. identify the structure and sequence of activities;
4. lay out a timeline to complete activities;
5. identify resources to achieve each goal;
6. locate a mentor/faculty member to provide feedback on the plan.

In addition, developing self-directed learners requires a scaffolded approach that may include starting with more self-paced activities and providing guidance to the learner on how to be more self-regulated. Health professions programs may employ several educational components may help develop SDL [5]: flipped classrooms (blended learning), learning contracts (an agreement between a learner and teacher that details what is to be learned, how it will be learnt, and how that learning will be verified), and minimal-guidance instruction (what people learn best in an unguided or minimally guided environment). *Learning is applied to real-life problems through project-based assessments, which emphasize problem-solving and independent application. Assessments assess critical thinking skills and application skills through open-ended questions, case studies, and adaptive assessments. Feedback is provided through formative assessments, goals are aligned through learning contracts, and final reflections claim the learning journey to have been successful [7].*

For SDL learners will need guidance: they will have the opportunity to learn, formulate learning strategies, reflect (repeat) what they have learned, self-assess, and more. Indeed, the technology of combining an individual’s independent activities in foreign language learning with creative activity, that is, the technology of directing the student to SDL is an important component of the educational process. On this issue Arkhangelsky S.I., Burdenyuk G.M., Vezhbitsky A.A., Zinovyev S.I., Nikandrov N.D., Pidkasistiy P.I. and other scientists have conducted research and interpreted the term independent work in different contexts, however, the exact explanation for independent work or a scientific methodology of managing students’ independent work has not been fully developed.

Students’ Independent Work (SIW) or self-study is a student-specific study activity, which allows him to perform didactic tasks independently, interest in reading and increase knowledge in a particular field of science focused. The content of SIW is related to the performance of practical tasks that allow to form logical thinking, creative activity, a research approach in the development of educational material [4; 34].

In the process of teaching foreign languages, their own culture, national values, customs, etc. the language is compared with the cultural units of the country being studied. For example, students are given the task of studying national handicraft traditions. By implementing this technology in small groups on the basis of various tasks, the participation of all students is ensured, the amount of information is increased, time is saved. Therefore, in this technological process, students use the Internet, encyclopedias and specialized literature, interview people in the field to better understand the secrets of the craft, study, design, summarize, summarize and creatively approach the collected materials, that is, independently prepare for the presentation. As a result, students develop creative activity, initiative, research skills, intellectual ability and creative potential [2, 101].

In the following some various methodological recommendations that help to improve independent teaching in foreign languages are given:

- *ensuring the continuity of independent work in the education system;*
 - *developing independent work monitoring;*
 - *following the logical connection in the topics and exercises;*
 - *preparation for practical training and study of video materials;*
 - *studying, searching and obtaining new information on the Internet;*
 - *forum - telegram channels or remote control on science topics exchanging of views on educational platforms;*
 - *consolidation of materials related to the science module with test tasks;*
 - *preparation of assignments for the established controls on the subject;*
 - *inclusion of creative, logical tasks and communicative exercises in educational and methodical complexes;*
 - *introduction of modular teaching technology for independent work in the classroom.*

In conclusion, the microsystems of continuing education will increase the quality of education through the effective organization and improvement of independent work in schools, secondary special and higher education institutions, and the task of providing competitive specialists will be fully fulfilled. During the self-directed learning process, the learner sets goals, determines how progress will be assessed, defines the structure and sequence of activities and a timeline, identifies resources, and seeks out feedback. As a valuable lifelong learning skill, self-directed learning can serve as the basis for a successful lifelong learning journey and career.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We built free and flourishing, democratic government together. Tashkent, Uzbekistan. 2016, p.56.
2. Anderson L.S. The integration of technology in the 21st Century classroom. Mississippi, 2013, p.200.
3. Bach K., Harnish R.M. Linguistic communication and speech acts - Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2002, p.420.
4. Brockett RG, Hiemstra R. Self-Direction in Adult Learning. Routledge; 2018. Accessed September 12, 2023. [DOI]
5. [Jennifer D Robinson](#)^{a,✉}, [Adam M Persky](#)^{b,c} Developing Self-Directed Learners American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7159015/>
6. Knowles MS. Self-Directed Learning: A Guide for Learners and Teachers. Chicago: Association Press; 1975.
7. Taylor TAH, Kemp K, Mi M, Lerchenfeldt S. Self-directed learning assessment practices in undergraduate health professions education: a systematic review. Med Educ Online. 2023;28(1):2189553. [DOI]